

Myth 1: Preprints aren't peer-reviewed, so they must be low quality

YouTube Description Box

 This #PeerReviewWeek, we are tackling a common misconception: “Preprints aren't peer-reviewed, so they must be poor quality.” Let's dig into the evidence to show why that's not true:

- ✓ Preprints speed up science by making findings freely available to all
- ✓ Preprint servers often screen for plagiarism, ethical concerns, and scientific scope before posting
- ✓ Nearly 70% of preprints are later published in peer-reviewed journals—usually with only minor changes
- ✓ Preprints invite open, community-wide feedback
- ✓ Peer review is valuable but not perfect, and all research benefits from ongoing scrutiny

References and resources

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Script

Camera 1-2

Welcome to the ASAPbio Myth Busting Series.

You've probably heard the claim: “Preprints aren't peer-reviewed, so they must be poor quality.” Is this really true? Let's take a closer look.

Camera 3

Preprints are research papers shared openly before journal publication. They speed up the communication of science and make findings accessible to everyone—no costs to authors, no

paywalls for readers.

Camera 4-6

It's true that preprints don't go through traditional journal peer review before they are posted. But that does **NOT** mean they are completely unvetted. Most preprint servers screen submissions for plagiarism, ethical concerns, and basic scientific scope. While this is not a detailed quality review, it does mean that preprints are far from "anything goes."

Camera 7

Here is an important fact: most preprints are eventually published in peer-reviewed journals. A large study of over 18 thousand preprints posted on bioRxiv between 2013 and 2017 found that nearly 70% were subsequently published in peer-reviewed journals¹. When researchers compared preprints with their journal published versions, they found that most do not differ substantially. The core findings and data remain stable^{2,3}. This suggests that many preprints often begin with a high level of quality, and that journal-organized peer review mostly adds small refinements rather than major overhauls.

Camera 8-9

Preprints also open the door for new approaches to peer review. Once a preprint is posted, scientists anywhere in the world can comment, highlight key findings, and suggest improvements. Platforms like PRereview and preLights make this feedback more visible and structured. In fact, preprints can facilitate feedback from a wider and more diverse community than the traditional two to four journal reviewers.

Camera 10-11

Now let's flip the lens and look at peer review itself. Peer review is important—it helps refine research—but it **isn't** a guarantee of accuracy. Studies have shown that journal-organized peer review can be slow, inconsistent, and subject to human bias. In some instances, reviewers do not agree more than would occur by chance⁴. That's why journal publication should not be mistaken as a seal of absolute truth, and why preprints and journal articles both benefit from

¹ Fraser N, Momeni F, Mayr P, Peters I. 2020. The relationship between bioRxiv preprints, citations and altmetrics. *Quant Sci Stud* 1–21. doi:10.1162/qss_a_00043

² Klein M, Broadwell P, Farb SE, Grappone T. 2019. Comparing published scientific journal articles to their pre-print versions. *Int J Digit Libr* 20:335–350. doi:10.1007/s00799-018-0234-1

³ Brierley L, Nanni F, Polka JK, Dey G, Pálffy M, Fraser N, Coates JA. 2022. Tracking changes between preprint posting and journal publication during a pandemic. *PLoS Biol* 20:e3001285. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.3001285

⁴ Rothwell PM, Martyn CN. 2000. Reproducibility of peer review in clinical neuroscience. Is agreement between reviewers any greater than would be expected by chance alone? *Brain* 123 (Pt 9):1964–1969. doi:10.1093/brain/123.9.1964

ongoing scrutiny and discussion.

So where does this leave us? Whether you're reading a preprint or a journal article, the same responsibility applies: read critically. Look at the methods, data, and reasoning. Ask whether the conclusions follow from the evidence. Also, look for related studies, both supporting and contradictory, for additional context. That's how science moves forward.

Camera 12-13

So, are preprints of low-quality? No, they are an essential part of today's scientific ecosystem—they offer a democratic process for accelerating research dissemination, inviting open feedback, and speeding up discovery.

In short: preprints are not the end of quality control, but the beginning of scientific conversation

Camera 14

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